

A critical analysis of Online Communication Pattern among Adolescent Students

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Abstract

Adolescents are very active users of Social Networking Site where they are seen building social networks or social relations with SNS users who share same interests, activities, backgrounds or real-life connections. Adolescents use Social Networking Sites for different reasons. They use them for entertainment and sharing other social and political issues. However, there are certain topics which catch their interest are adolescents are seen discussing then on their Social platforms. The present study aims to know about the topics of their great interest and how such discussions help them to upgrade the level of social concerned. The present study is made on 400 adolescent students of Meerut City where 211 respondents are male and 189 female. Questionnaire method is used to collect the primary data and secondary data is collected from the studies which are conducted earlier in this field. The data is analysed using SPSS software and Chi-test is used to find the association among gender regarding topics discussed while using Social Networking Sites.

Keywords: Adolescents, Social Networking Sites, online discussion, Communication

Introduction:

We can define Social Media as a platform which enables people to interact and socially connect to other people in the society and around the world. It is the medium through which we communicate and share our opinions on everything under the sun. Facebook is the most preferred social media platform. With more than 2000 million Facebook users over the world, if a country is constituted with them, it would be the world's third largest, behind China and India. The other popular social media platforms are You Tube, Instagram, X (formally Twitter), WhatsApp etc. Social media provides a global platform to express one's views and ideas without any reservations or biasness. Through Social media, youth is exchanging ideas & views in a win-win situation. Youth are gaining much better perspectives, when it comes to cultural differences and misunderstandings. It promotes interpersonal communication and group dynamics while eliminating the barriers to communication. It has the ability to connect people across the world. Social media sites such as LinkedIn help job seekers to find jobs and builds professional connections across the globe. It is an easy source to promote education and help students via YouTube e-learning sessions or applications such as Unacademy. One of the significant impacts of social media is the tremendously increased awareness of the masses in context of the news and happenings going all around the world because internet spreads news and reviews more rapidly than any other mode and social media makes them do so.

Research Methodology:

The study is made over 400 respondents of Meerut city among which 211 respondents are males and 189 respondents are females. The age group of the respondents is 14-18 years of age. Questionnaire method is used to collect the primary data and secondary data is collected from the studies which are conducted earlier in this field. The data is analysed using SPSS software and chi-test is used to find out the association among gender and topics discussed by adolescents while using Social Networking Sites.

Topics discussed over Social Networking Sites by Adolescents:

1. Religious issues:

Gender * Religious Crosstabulation

Count

		Religious					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	24	23	37	23	104	211
	Female	28	17	46	20	78	189
Total		52	40	83	43	182	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.912 ^a	4	.296
Likelihood Ratio	4.915	4	.296
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.139	1	.144
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 1

Figure 1

Most of the adolescents share religious topics on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 13% always, 10% often, 20.8% sometimes, 10.8% rarely share religious topics on SNS. However, 45.5% adolescents never share religious topics on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share religious topics on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 4.912$; $p = .296$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no significant difference among the categories. It means that both males and females equally share religious topics through SNS.

2. India Pakistan relations:

Gender * IPRelation Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	29	25	26	39	92	211
	Female	36	16	25	39	73	189
Total		65	41	51	78	165	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.738 ^a	4	.443
Likelihood Ratio	3.749	4	.441
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.000	1	.317
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 2

Figure 2

Most of the adolescents share about India Pakistan Relation on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 16.3% always, 10.3% often and 12.8% sometimes, 19.5% rarely share about India Pakistan Relation on SNS. However, 41.3% adolescents never share about India Pakistan Relation on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about India Pakistan Relation on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 3.738$; $p = .443$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females equally prefer to share about India Pakistan Relation through SNS.

3. **India and China border issues:**

Gender * China Crosstabulation

		China					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	13	19	32	41	106	211
	Female	28	7	23	39	92	189
Total		41	26	55	80	198	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.366 ^a	4	.015
Likelihood Ratio	12.681	4	.013
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.066	1	.302
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 3

Figure 3

Most of the adolescents share about India China Border issue on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 10.3% always, 6.5% often, 13.8% sometimes and 20.0% rarely share about India China border issues on SNS. However, 49.5% adolescents never share about India China

border issues on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about India China border issue on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 12.366$; $p = .015$) where $p < .05$; it is statistically proved that there is association among the gender and the number of males and females vary in sharing about India China border issues through SNS.

4. India and Non Asian countries relationship:

Gender * Non Asian Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Non Asian					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	23	12	33	40	103	211
	Female	26	12	41	28	82	189
Total		49	24	74	68	185	400

Table 4

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.353 ^a	4	.360
Likelihood Ratio	4.357	4	.360
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.335	1	.127
N of Valid Cases	400		

Figure 4

Most of the adolescents share about India and Non-Asian countries Relation on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 12.3% always, 6.0% often and 18.5% sometimes, 17.0% rarely share about India and Non-Asian countries Relation on SNS. However, 46.3% adolescents never share about India and Non-Asian countries Relation on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about India and Non-Asian countries Relation on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 4.353$; $p = .360$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no significant difference among the categories which means there is no association and both males and females equally share about India and Non-Asian countries Relation through SNS.

5. Indian security arrangements:

Gender * Security Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Security					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	39	34	28	20	90	211
	Female	41	29	30	18	71	189
Total		80	63	58	38	161	400

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.658 ^a	4	.798
Likelihood Ratio	1.658	4	.798
Linear-by-Linear Association	.973	1	.324
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 5

Figure 5

The adolescents are active to share about Indian security arrangements on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 20.0% always, 15.8% often and 14.5% sometimes, 9.5% rarely share about Indian security arrangement on SNS. However, 40.3% adolescents never share about Indian security on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about Indian security on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 1.658$; $p = .798$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females are active in sharing about Indian security issues through SNS.

6. Political instability:

Gender * Instability Crosstabulation

		Instability					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	55	47	46	36	27	211
	Female	60	42	28	37	22	189
Total		115	89	74	73	49	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.203 ^a	4	.379
Likelihood Ratio	4.235	4	.375
Linear-by-Linear Association	.643	1	.423
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 6

Figure 6

Most of the adolescents share about Political Instability on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 28.8% always, 22.3% often and 18.5% sometimes, 18.3% rarely share about Political Instability on SNS. However, 12.3% adolescents never share about this topic on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about political instability on SNS is

much more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 4.203$; $p = .379$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females equally share about political instability through SNS.

7. Corruption

Gender * Corruption Crosstabulation

		Corruption					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	67	33	54	34	23	211
	Female	70	20	52	24	23	189
Total		137	53	106	58	46	400

Figure 7

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.818 ^a	4	.431
Likelihood Ratio	3.847	4	.427
Linear-by-Linear Association	.212	1	.645
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 7

The adolescents are quite active to share about corruption on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 34.3% always, 13.3% often and 26.5% sometimes, 14.5% rarely share about corruption on SNS. However, 11.5% adolescents never share about Corruption on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about Corruption on SNS is more than those who never share about it on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 3.818$; $p = .431$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females equally share about corruption through SNS.

8. Local Government administration

Gender * LocalGov Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		LocalGov					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	48	38	40	51	34	211
	Female	51	26	31	33	48	189
Total		99	64	71	84	82	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.545 ^a	4	.074
Likelihood Ratio	8.577	4	.073
Linear-by-Linear Association	.266	1	.606
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 8

Figure 8

The respondents share about local Government on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 24.8% always, 16.0% often and 17.8% sometimes, 21.0% rarely share about local Government on SNS. However, 20.5% adolescents never share about local Government on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about local Government on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 8.545$; $p = .074$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no significant difference among the categories. It means that both males and females equally share about local Government through SNS.

9. Policies of Government

Gender * PolGov Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		PolGov					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	56	45	61	21	28	211
	Female	59	21	55	22	32	189
Total		115	66	116	43	60	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.221 ^a	4	.084
Likelihood Ratio	8.399	4	.078
Linear-by-Linear Association	.507	1	.476
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 9

Figure 9

The adolescents are interested to share about Government policies on SNS. Here, 28.8% always, 16.5% often and 29.0% sometimes, 10.8% rarely share about it on SNS. However, 15.0% adolescents never share about policies of Government on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about policies of Government on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 8.221$; $p = .084$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the gender and both males and females equally share about Policies of Government through SNS.

10. Price hike in petrol

Gender * Petrol Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	59	28	70	20	34	211
	Female	60	22	50	9	48	189
Total		119	50	120	29	82	400

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.443 ^a	4	.051
Likelihood Ratio	9.549	4	.049
Linear-by-Linear Association	.289	1	.591
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 10

Figure 10

The issue of price hike of petrol is often discussed on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 29.8% always, 12.5% often and 30.0% sometimes, 7.3% rarely share about price hike of petrol on SNS. However, 20.5% adolescents never share about this topic on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about price hike of petrol on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 9.443$; $p = .051$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no significant difference among the categories which means both males and females equally share about price hike of petrol through SNS.

11. Price hike in transport

Gender * Transport Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Transport					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	53	38	63	22	35	211
	Female	55	22	55	7	50	189
Total		108	60	118	29	85	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.084 ^a	4	.007
Likelihood Ratio	14.497	4	.006
Linear-by-Linear Association	.613	1	.434
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 11

Figure 11

Most of the adolescents share about price hike in transport on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 27.0% always, 15.0% often and 29.5% sometimes, 7.3% rarely share about price hike of transport on SNS. However, 21.3% adolescents never share such topic on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about price hike in transport on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 14.084$; $p = .007$) where $p < .05$; it is statistically proved that there is significant difference among the categories which means there is association among categories and males are more active in sharing this topic than females on SNS.

12. Job opportunities

Gender * Job Crosstabulation

		Job					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	56	76	36	17	26	211
	Female	57	49	34	25	24	189
Total		113	125	70	42	50	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.311 ^a	4	.177
Likelihood Ratio	6.347	4	.175
Linear-by-Linear Association	.432	1	.511
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 12

Figure 12

Adolescents share about job opportunities on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 28.3% always, 31.3% often and 17.5% sometimes, 10.5% rarely share about job opportunity on SNS. However, 12.5% adolescents never share about such topic on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about job opportunity on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 6.311$; $p = .177$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females share about job opportunities through SNS.

13. Recent developments in IT education

Gender * IT Crosstabulation

		IT					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	63	78	40	10	20	211
	Female	58	62	42	9	18	189
Total		121	140	82	19	38	400

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.035 ^a	4	.904
Likelihood Ratio	1.035	4	.904
Linear-by-Linear Association	.046	1	.830
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 13

Figure 13

Most of the adolescents share about development in IT education on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 30.3% always, 35.0% often and 20.5% sometimes, 4.8% rarely share about this topic on SNS. However, 9.5% adolescents never share about development in IT on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about this topic on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 1.035$; $p = .904$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females equally share about this topic on SNS.

14. Education

Gender * education Crosstabulation

		education					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	92	70	37	4	8	211
	Female	89	45	33	11	11	189
Total		181	115	70	15	19	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.268 ^a	4	.082
Likelihood Ratio	8.419	4	.077
Linear-by-Linear Association	.890	1	.345
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 14

Figure 14

Adolescents use SNS effectively to share educational topics. Here, 45.3% always, 28.8% often and 17.5% sometimes, 3.8% rarely share about education on SNS. However, 4.8% adolescents never share about education on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about education on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 8.268$; $p = .082$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females share about education through SNS.

15. Status of your educational institution

Gender * eduInst Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		eduInst					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	69	51	62	16	13	211
	Female	70	38	41	18	22	189
Total		139	89	103	34	35	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.432 ^a	4	.115
Likelihood Ratio	7.472	4	.113
Linear-by-Linear Association	.423	1	.515
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 15

Figure 15

The adolescents share about the status of educational institution on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 34.8% always, 22.3% often and 25.8% sometimes, 8.5% rarely share about the status of educational institution on SNS. However, 8.8% adolescents never share about

such topic on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about the status of educational institution on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 7.432$; $p = .115$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the categories and both males and females equally share about the status of educational institution through SNS.

16. Recent trend in fashion technology

Gender * Trend Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	73	53	48	15	22	211
	Female	59	44	49	11	26	189
Total		132	97	97	26	48	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.075 ^a	4	.722
Likelihood Ratio	2.075	4	.722
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.109	1	.292
N of Valid Cases	400		

Figure 16

Adolescents are quite active to share about recent trend on “Social Networking Sites”. Here,

33.0% always, 24.3% often and 24.3% sometimes, 6.5% rarely share about recent trend on SNS. However, 12.0% adolescents never share about recent trend on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about this on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 2.075$; $p = .722$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no significant difference among the categories and both males and females share about recent trend through SNS.

17. Pollution

Gender * Pollution Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		Pollution					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	48	45	69	27	22	211
	Female	50	24	67	20	28	189
Total		98	69	136	47	50	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.035 ^a	4	.134
Likelihood Ratio	7.122	4	.130
Linear-by-Linear Association	.358	1	.550
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 17

Figure 17

Most of the adolescents share about pollution on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 24.5%

always, 17.3% often and 34.0% sometimes, 11.8% rarely share about pollution on SNS. However, 12.5% adolescents never share about pollution on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share about this topic on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 7.035$; $p = .134$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no significant difference among the categories and both males and females share about pollution through SNS.

18. Sports

Gender * sport Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		sport					
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	78	62	47	8	16	211
	Female	72	53	36	9	19	189
Total		150	115	83	17	35	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.513 ^a	4	.824
Likelihood Ratio	1.513	4	.824
Linear-by-Linear Association	.165	1	.685
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 18

Figure 18

Most of the adolescents have sports related discussions on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 37.5% always, 28.8% often and 20.8% sometimes, 4.3% rarely share about sports on SNS. However, 8.8% adolescents never share about sports on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who have sports related discussion on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 1.513$; $p = .824$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the gender and both males and females are equally involved in sports discussions on SNS.

19. Campaign for a movement/Product/Thought

Gender * Thought Crosstabulation

		Thought					Total
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	
Gender	Male	61	34	46	36	34	211
	Female	55	24	39	28	43	189
Total		116	58	85	64	77	400

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.463 ^a	4	.483
Likelihood Ratio	3.467	4	.483
Linear-by-Linear Association	.893	1	.345
N of Valid Cases	400		

Table 19

Figure 19

Social Sites are used effectively for joining people in campaign or movement. Most of the adolescents share about campaign on “Social Networking Sites”. Here, 29.0% always, 14.5% often and 21.3% sometimes, 16.0% rarely share about some campaign on SNS. However, 19.3% adolescents never share about campaign on SNS. Overall, the percentage of adolescents who share campaign on SNS is more than those who never share such topic on SNS.

The chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 3.463$; $p = .483$) where $p > .05$; it is statistically proved that there is no association among the gender and both males and females share about campaign through SNS.

Findings:

1. Male and Female respondents equally share religious topics through “Social Networking Sites”.
2. Male and Female respondents equally share about India Pakistan Relation through “Social

Networking Sites”.

3. There is significant difference among gender in sharing about India China border issues through “Social Networking Sites”.
4. Male and Female respondents equally share about India and Non-Asian countries relation through “Social Networking Sites”.
5. Both males and females are active in sharing about Indian security arrangements through “Social Networking Sites”.
6. Male and Female respondents equally share about political instability through “Social Networking Sites”.
7. Both male and female respondents equally share about corruption through “Social Networking Sites”.
8. Male and Female respondents equally share about local Government administration through “Social Networking Sites”.
9. Policies of the Government are equally shared by both male and female respondents through “Social Networking Sites”.
10. Male and Female respondents equally share about price hike of petrol through “Social Networking Sites”.
11. There is significant difference among gender in sharing about price hike in transport through “Social Networking Sites”.
12. Both male and female respondents share about job opportunities through “Social Networking Sites”.
13. Male and female respondents equally share about recent development in IT education through “Social Networking Sites”.
14. Both males and females share about education through SNS.
15. Both male and female respondents share about status of educational institution through “Social Networking Sites”.
16. Male and female respondents are active in sharing about trends in fashion through “Social Networking Sites”.
17. Both male and female respondents are active in sharing about pollution through “Social Networking Sites”.
18. Male and female respondents are equally involved in sports discussions on “Social Networking Sites”.
19. Male and female respondents equally share about campaign through “Social

Networking Sites”.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

1. Adolescent takes interests in political and social issues. Social sites prove to be an open platform for political discussions.
2. Government can make use of Social Sites to promote its new policies. It will also help in making perception among young voters.
3. Educational institutes can promote achievements of their institute by collaborating with the students.
4. Adolescent become active members of social campaigns when promoted online.
5. Adolescent actively search for job opportunities online. Job portals must regularly post new openings for young job seekers.

References:

1. Barnes, S. (2007). A privacy paradox: social networking in the United States: *First Monday*, 9, 11-17.
2. Barton, K. M. (2009). *Reality television programming and diverging gratifications: The influence of content on gratifications obtained*. *Journal of Broadcast & Electronic Media*, 53 (3), 460-476.
3. Beer, D. (2008). *Social network(ing) sites...revisiting the story so far: A response to Danah Boyd & Nicole Ellison*. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*: 13, 2 (2008), 516-529.
4. Berg, J., Berquam, L. & Christopher, K. (2007). *Social Networking Technologies: A —Poke for Campus Services*, *Educause Review*: March/April 32-44.
5. Asilo, John Manuel C. Manlapig, Justine Angeli P. Rementilla, Jeremiah Josh R. (2010). *The Influence of Social Networking Sites on the Interpersonal Relationships of Rogationist College Students*. Available at: <http://www.scribd.com/doc/27327211/The-Influence-of-Social-Networking-Sites-to-Interpersonal-Relationships-of-the-Students-of-Rogationist-College-High-School-Department-S-Y-2009-2010#scribd>
6. Charnigo L. and Barnett-Ellis P. (2007). *Checking Out Facebook.com: The Impact of a Digital Trend on Academic Libraries*, *Information Technology and Libraries*, 23-33.
7. Castells M, Ardevol MF, Quiu JL and Sey A (2007). *Mobile Communication and Society: a global Perspective*. p.7, MIT Press: Cambridge MA.
8. IMAI Press Release - 17 November, 2015. *India To Cross 400 Million Internet Users By Dec'15*. Available at: <http://www.iamai.in/media/details/4486>